

THE POSITION AND ROLE OF FAIRY TALES IN TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR THROUGH INDIVIDUAL AND GROUP WORK AND ITS PRACTICAL APPLICATION

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Abstract. *In modern pedagogical practice, the communicative method of learning English is given special attention. It is considered to be the most effective method of language learning, allowing students to master the intricacies of the English language in an entertaining and unobtrusive way. In this article, the effective use of fairy tales in teaching English is aimed at revealing new ways of learning the language, especially grammatical aspects, using fairy tales by working individually or in groups.*

Key words: *English language, fairy tales, student, individual, group, skills, methods and efficiency.*

МЕСТО И РОЛЬ СКАЗОК В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ГРАММАТИКЕ ЧЕРЕЗ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНУЮ И ГРУППОВУЮ РАБОТУ И ЕЕ ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ

Аннотация: *В современной педагогической практике особое внимание уделяется коммуникативному методу изучения английского языка. Считается наиболее эффективным методом изучения языка, позволяющим студентам в занимательной и ненавязчивой форме осваивать тонкости английского языка.*

В данной статье эффективное использование сказок в обучении английскому языку направлено на выявление новых способов изучения языка, особенно грамматических аспектов, с использованием сказок путем индивидуальной или групповой работы.

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, сказки, ученик, личность, группа, навыки, методы и эффективность.*

Today it is believed that during the study of English, students should master not only all language skills, but also have a visual representation of the traditions, culture, history, realities of life of the inhabitants of English-speaking countries.

English fairy tales are quite suitable for this purpose. I will say even more, the use of English fairy tales in the classroom improves individual and group learning, contributes to the development of grammar knowledge.

It is necessary to strive to ensure that students receive satisfaction not only from the plot of the fairy tale, but also from the realization that they understand in English what it tells about. The indisputable advantage of using a fairy tale as a method of teaching English is the impression and emotional uplift from the information received.

The effectiveness of using a fairy tale in teaching speech depends not only on the exact definition of its place in the learning system, but also on how rationally the structure of the lesson is organized, how the learning opportunities of the fairy tale are coordinated with the learning objectives. In the structure of the lesson for teaching oral speech, four stages can be distinguished:

- 1) preparatory - the stage of preliminary removal of linguistic and linguistic and cultural difficulties;
- 2) the perception of a fairy tale during the initial reading - the development of skills for the perception of information;
- 3) control of understanding of the main content;
- 4) development of language skills and oral speech skills.

The fourth stage may be preceded by a second reading.

The undoubted advantages of fairy tales are their:

- 1) authenticity;
- 2) informative saturation;
- 3) concentration of language means;
- 4) emotional impact on trainees, etc.

The effectiveness of the use of fairy tales depends on the rational organization of classes.

Pre-text exercises (work on the words and grammar used in the text).

1. Find pairs: a word and its definition. Students are given 2 columns, their task is to connect the pairs with arrows.
2. Choose the antonym of the word from those offered. For example, large - big, small, black.
3. Choose a synonym for the word from the proposed group. For example, can't stand - to love, to hate, to stand.
4. Connect pairs of words by meaning into phrases, for example, match the words for animals with the words for places. Animals: a fox, a dog, a tiger. Places: a zoo, a forest, a house
5. Work with prepositions. For example, fill in the gaps with necessary prepositions.
6. Paraphrase sentences using a specific grammatical structure. For example, say that it is wrong - use negative sentences.
7. Paraphrase the sentences, replacing the highlighted word or expression with a synonym used in the text.

Fairy Tales in Teaching Grammar can be introduced in a number of ways. There is a great opportunity of using a “real texts” to understand and experiment with a “real language”. Children have an innate sense of interest in stories that portray heroes, personify animals and actions, take place in castles and enchanted forests. Fairy tales will interest pupils and bring them into a natural rhythm, flow and picturesque language of the text (Jones & Allen, 1996). In fairy tales two main uses of language can be distinguished: for a narrative and for a dialogue. A narrative text concerns the series of events: Hans started to pull out his finger; little brother ran for help. A dialogue is type of language as if it is spoken by the characters: “Run! Go to the town and tell the men there's a hole in the dike!”(Cameron, 2001). The teacher can point out the use of the Past Simple in narratives and the Present Simple in dialogues. Fairy tales help children to notice language areas such as past tenses, adjectives, comparatives and etc. Teachers could use passages from the fairy tale to point out grammatical features. For example, to ask students to find irregular verbs, to write down all adjectives or to locate the words and phrases that indicates position in place or time. Texts with continuous meanings are more authentic than the connected sentences which are often used as examples in grammar books. Story books often contain extended examples of dialogue that use a wide variety of punctuation marks, in more natural context than is possible in grammar exercise books. Word-order can be taught through reading fairy tales as well. When working in groups,

students can ask and answer content-related questions and learn the word-order of questions and affirmative sentences (Reid, 2002)

Fairy Tales in Teaching Grammar

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Grammar

(Activities to present and compare adjectives)

Exercise 1:

- The teacher asks pupils to look at exercise 1. The teacher reads the instruction and explains the task.
- The teacher gives pupils enough time to complete the task.
- Answers:

Iceberg is as big as house.

My bracelet is as beautiful as your bracelet.

Today it is as cold as it was yesterday.

My car is as fast as your car.

A train is as comfortable as a bus.

The teacher checks answers together with pupils.

Fairy tales and cartoons. While learning a foreign language, children do not understand the words in the cartoon, but they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

Currently, all kindergartens in China are equipped with multimedia devices. Children are taught English through songs, poems, stories, and videos. It turns boring language lessons into an interesting daily game. In Chinese kindergartens, there are about 10 students in one group, and the

teacher regularly uses the method of education based on the psychology of each child. This requires the educator not only to be an educator, but also to be an artist, musician, foreign language teacher, and a good psychologist mother. Of course, in today's developing era, the Chinese are creating great facilities for the young generation in this regard. Teaching through multimedia gives the educator great opportunities. In this way, it is possible to raise the interest of children to a high level and to attract their attention for a long time. Through this, we can see that children's language skills have increased. If our topic is "Animals", we first use their sounds to teach the names of different animals, children pay close attention to this. They look at them, and immediately they start saying the names of animals such as cat, tiger, bear....

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